

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS OF DAMAGE PROPAGATION REGARDING WOVEN CFRP LAMINATES BASED ON HOMOGENIZATION THEORY

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ABSTRACT

In this study, failure behavior of woven CFRP laminates with consideration of the elasto-viscoplasticity of the epoxy resin is investigated by the numerical simulation based on the finite element method and the homogenization theory. The elasto-viscoplastic constitutive equation considering damage development is newly proposed by applying damage model based on the continuum damage mechanics to the elasto-viscoplastic constitutive equation. An elliptic damage criterion and a second-order damage tensor are introduced to address an anisotropic damage property of fiber bundles. Moreover, with the constitutive equations applied to the homogenization theory, the microscopic and macroscopic constitutive equations are derived. Then, the uniaxial loading-unloading tests of the epoxy resin are conducted under several strain rates to identify the damage development equation and the elasto-viscoplastic properties. Next, a numerical demonstration of damage propagation for the woven CFRP laminates is performed under uniaxial loading condition. As a result, the macroscopic rigidity and stress gradually drop as a variety of damage mode occurs in stages.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRPs) have become an important structural material in industrial fields. In particular, woven composites have been used because of higher impact resistance and higher interlaminar fracture toughness than other composites such as unidirectional fiber reinforced composites [1]. On the other hand, it is difficult to comprehend damage propagation mechanics of the woven composites since they have three-dimensional textile structure. Therefore, understanding their damage propagation property is indispensable regarding lightweight design of products [2]. Establishment of the methods which evaluate damage propagation behavior of the woven composites by numerical analyses has been essential because tremendous time and effort are required to observe the variation of damage state under different loading conditions. Besides, the woven composites have many design variables,

e.g. a variety of textile structures such as plain, twill and satin weaves, shape, size, and volume fraction of fiber bundles. Some researchers investigated effects of these design variables on the mechanical properties [3].

However, the above evaluation of damage property for the woven composites by numerical simulation is still limited to the elastic analyses [4]. In fact, a matrix resin used for CFRPs has the viscoplastic property, and the nonlinear behavior of CFRPs was analyzed using the elasto-viscoplastic constitutive equation of the matrix resin [5]. Besides, the elasto-plastic damage development behavior of metal materials was also analyzed based on continuum damage mechanics [6]. In the continuum damage mechanics, the damage variable is considered to estimate a damage state. By introducing the damage variable into the elasto-viscoplastic constitutive equation, the viscoplastic deformation and damage development of the matrix resin can be evaluated simultaneously.

As for the numerical simulations of composite materials, the numerical costs become a problem in some situations because the composite materials generally consist from macro and micro scales. A mathematical homogenization theory is one of the useful methods to evaluate mechanical properties of materials which have periodicity in internal structure such as woven composites [7, 8]. This theory can analyze the macroscopic mechanical properties of composite materials from the microscopic structure and the constitutive equations of their constituent materials. Furthermore, the inelastic behavior of composite materials can also be considered by introducing the nonlinear constitutive equations. Thus, the elasto-viscoplastic constitutive equation considering damage development is introduced into the homogenization theory.

In this study, damage propagation of the woven CFRP laminates is simulated numerically based on the homogenization theory with the elasto-viscoplasticity taken into consideration. For this, uniaxial tensile tests including unloading and reloading phases of the epoxy resin are performed under several strain rates to obtain the elasto-viscoplastic and damage properties. Based on the proposed method, damage propagation behavior of the woven CFRP laminates under uniaxial tensile loading is evaluated macroscopically and microscopically.

2 BASIC THEORIES

2.1 Elasto-Viscoplastic Constitutive Equation Considering Damage Development

In order to evaluate mechanical behavior of the epoxy matrix, continuum damage mechanics is applied to the elasto-viscoplastic constitutive equation. The continuum damage mechanics introduces the damage variable which stands for damage state of materials. In this study, we employ the scalar damage variable and a hypothesis of strain equivalence. Assuming that the epoxy resin is an elasto-viscoplastic material and has isotropic damage property, the following equation is obtained.

$$\tilde{\sigma}_{ij} = C_{ijkl}^0 (\varepsilon_{kl} - \varepsilon_{kl}^p). \quad (1)$$

Here, $\tilde{\sigma}_{ij}$ is the effective stress tensor which is the stress expanded by damage, C_{ijkl}^0 is the initial elastic stiffness tensor, ε_{ij} and ε_{ij}^p are the total and plastic strain tensors. The effective stress tensor is described by following equation.

$$\tilde{\sigma}_{ij} = \frac{\sigma_{ij}}{1 - D}, \quad (2)$$

where σ_{ij} is the stress tensor, and D is the scalar damage variable which expresses damage state. $D = 0$ and 1 mean the undamaged and completely damaged states, respectively. Substituting Eq. (2) for Eq. (1), the following equation is obtained.

$$\sigma_{ij} = (1 - D) C_{ijkl}^0 (\varepsilon_{kl} - \varepsilon_{kl}^p). \quad (3)$$

Eq. (3) should be differentiated by time t because viscoplastic deformation depends on loading rate;

$$\dot{\sigma}_{ij} = (1 - D) C_{ijkl}^0 (\dot{\varepsilon}_{kl} - \dot{\varepsilon}_{kl}^p) - \frac{\dot{D}}{1 - D} \sigma_{ij}. \quad (4)$$

Here, $(\dot{\bullet})$ represents the differentiation with respect to t . To consider viscoplastic deformation, the hypothesis of strain equivalence is applied to the viscoplastic constitutive equation [5] and the plastic strain rate $\dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^p$ is replaced by the viscoplastic function β_{ij} as follows;

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^p = \beta_{ij} = \frac{3}{2} \dot{\varepsilon}_c \left[\frac{\sigma_{EQ}}{(1-D)g(p)} \right]^{1/m} \frac{\sigma_{ij}^D}{\sigma_{EQ}}. \quad (5)$$

Here, $\dot{\varepsilon}_c$ is the reference strain rate, m designates the strain rate sensitivity exponent, σ_{EQ} and σ_{ij}^D indicate Mises equivalent stress and the deviation stress tensor, respectively. $g(p)$ is the hardening function which depends on the equivalent plastic strain p and described as follows;

$$g(p) = \sigma_c \left(\frac{p}{\varepsilon_c} \right)^n + C. \quad (6)$$

For the above equation, σ_c and ε_c are the reference stress and strain, n indicates the work-hardening exponent, and C is the material parameter. In this study, the scalar damage variable D is assumed to develop with the equivalent plastic strain p , and thus the damage development equation is defined as

$$D = d_1 (p + d_2)^{d_3} - d_1 d_2^{d_3}, \quad (7)$$

where d_1 , d_2 and d_3 are the material parameters. Elastic, viscoplastic and damage parameters can be obtained from the uniaxial tests. Based on the hypothesis of strain equivalence, the scalar damage variable D is expressed by the initial elastic stiffness E_0 and the elastic stiffness of the damaged material E ,

$$D = 1 - \frac{E}{E_0}. \quad (8)$$

2.2 Damage Behavior of Fiber Bundles

In this study, the fiber bundles are assumed to be a transverse isotropic homogenous body because they can be regarded as unidirectional fiber reinforced plastics locally. Damage of the fiber bundles is judged by the in-plane biaxial elliptic criterion described by the following inequalities [9];

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \left(\frac{\sigma_L}{F_L^t} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_T}{F_T^t} \right)^2 \geq 1 \quad (\text{when } \sigma_L > 0 \cap \sigma_T > 0), \\ \left(\frac{\sigma_L}{F_L^c} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_T}{F_T^t} \right)^2 \geq 1 \quad (\text{when } \sigma_L < 0 \cap \sigma_T > 0), \\ \left(\frac{\sigma_L}{F_L^c} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_T}{F_T^c} \right)^2 \geq 1 \quad (\text{when } \sigma_L < 0 \cap \sigma_T < 0), \\ \left(\frac{\sigma_L}{F_L^t} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_T}{F_T^c} \right)^2 \geq 1 \quad (\text{when } \sigma_L > 0 \cap \sigma_T < 0). \end{array} \right. \quad (9)$$

Eq. (9) is graphically explained in Figure 1. Here, σ_i and F_i^j are stress and uniaxial strength, where subscript L and T indicate longitudinal and transverse directions, and superscript t and c refer to tension and compression.

After a fiber bundle element is judged as a damaged element by the elliptic criterion (9), its damage mode is decided by a stress to strength ratio shown in Table 1. Here, mode L means fiber fracture, while mode T means transverse crack (matrix or interface cracks). We consider a stress component with the maximum stress to strength ratio to be dominant and decide the damage mode. Accordingly, the occurrence of damage and the damage mode is decided in $\sigma_L - \sigma_T$ plane as shown in Figure 1. Furthermore, the judgment of damage for the damaged elements is continued until the damage in another mode occurs.

 Figure 1: Elliptic criterion and damage mode in $\sigma_L - \sigma_T$ plane.

Table 1: Relation between damage modes and stress to strength ratios.

Damage mode	Mode L	Mode T
Stress to strength ratio	$\frac{\sigma_L}{F_L^t}$ or $\frac{\sigma_L}{F_L^c}$	$\frac{\sigma_T}{F_T^t}$ or $\frac{\sigma_T}{F_T^c}$

In this study, the second-order damage tensor [10] is employed to handle the anisotropic damage of the fiber bundles. Elastic stiffness tensor of damaged materials \mathbf{C} is derived based on a hypothesis of strain energy equivalence as follow;

$$\mathbf{C} = \begin{bmatrix} d_1^2 C_{1111}^0 & d_1 d_2 C_{1122}^0 & d_1 d_3 C_{1133}^0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & d_2^2 C_{2222}^0 & d_2 d_3 C_{2233}^0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & d_3^2 C_{3333}^0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & & d_{23} C_{2323}^0 & 0 & 0 \\ \text{sym.} & & & & d_{31} C_{3131}^0 & 0 \\ & & & & & d_{12} C_{1212}^0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (10)$$

where d_i and d_{ij} are described with the principal values of the damage tensor D_i ($i = 1, 2, 3$);

$$d_i = 1 - D_i, \quad d_{ij} = \left\{ \frac{2(1 - D_i)(1 - D_j)}{(1 - D_i) + (1 - D_j)} \right\}^2. \quad (11)$$

In case a fiber bundle element is judged as a damaged element by the elliptic criterion and the damage mode is decided by the stress to strength ratio, its corresponding damage variable D_i is changed from 0 into 1 which stands for a damaged state.

2.3 Homogenization Theory

In this study, the numerical analysis of damage propagation is conducted by applying the elasto-viscoplastic constitutive equation considering damage development into the homogenization theory. In the homogenization theory, analysis objects are considered in two scales which are homogenized macroscopic and heterogenous microscopic structures. Therefore, this theory can evaluate homogenized properties of composite materials and microscopic stress and strain distributions simultaneously.

In the homogenization theory, the unit cell Y is defined as the smallest representative volume element of periodic structures, and Cartesian coordinates y_i ($i = 1, 2, 3$) are defined for the unit cell. First, the microscopic displacement rate \dot{u}_i in the unit cell Y is expressed by the macroscopic displacement rate

gradient $\dot{F}_{ij} = \partial \dot{u}_i / \partial y_j$ and the microscopic perturbed displacement rate $\dot{u}_i^\#$;

$$\dot{u}_i = \dot{F}_{ij} y_j + \dot{u}_i^\# \quad (12)$$

Here, $\dot{u}_i^\#$ distributes periodically in the unit cell, which is called Y -periodicity. Considering the definition of strain, the following equation is obtained by differentiating Eq. (12).

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_{ij} = \dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^H + \dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^\# \quad (13)$$

where $\dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^H$ and $\dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^\#$ denote the macroscopic and perturbed strain rates;

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^H = \frac{1}{2} (\dot{F}_{ij} + \dot{F}_{ji}), \quad (14)$$

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^\# = \frac{1}{2} (\dot{u}_{i,j}^\# + \dot{u}_{j,i}^\#). \quad (15)$$

Here, $(\bullet)_{,i}$ represents the differentiation with respect to y_i .

The equilibrium of σ_{ij} is described in a rate form as;

$$\dot{\sigma}_{ij,j} = 0. \quad (16)$$

The integration by parts and the divergence theorem allow Eq. (16) to be transformed to a weak form;

$$\int_Y u_{i,j}^* \dot{\sigma}_{ij} dV - \int_{\Gamma_Y} u_i^* \dot{\sigma}_{ij} n_j dS = 0, \quad (17)$$

where u_i^* indicates a microscopic arbitrary displacement which satisfies Y -periodicity, Γ_Y denotes the boundary of Y , and n_i signifies the outward unit vector normal to Γ_Y . The periodicity of $\dot{\sigma}_{ij}$ and u_i^* enable the second term on the left-hand side of Eq. (17) to vanish;

$$\int_Y u_{i,j}^* \dot{\sigma}_{ij} dV = 0. \quad (18)$$

Subsequently, the following equation is obtained by substituting Eqs. (4) and (13) into Eq. (18);

$$\int_Y u_{i,j}^* C_{ijpq} \dot{u}_{p,q}^\# dV = -\dot{\varepsilon}_{kl}^H \int_Y u_{i,j}^* C_{ijkl} dV + \int_Y u_{i,j}^* C_{ijkl} \beta_{kl} dV + \int_Y u_{i,j}^* \frac{\dot{D}}{1-D} \sigma_{ij} dV. \quad (19)$$

Here, it is assumed the perturbed displacement rate $\dot{u}_i^\#$ is described with the characteristic functions χ_i^{kl} , φ_i , and ψ_i ;

$$\dot{u}_i^\# = \chi_i^{kl} \dot{\varepsilon}_{kl}^H + \varphi_i + \psi_i. \quad (20)$$

Consequently, the characteristic functions result in the elastic, viscoplastic and damage boundary value problems as follow;

$$\int_Y u_{i,j}^* C_{ijpq} \chi_{p,q}^{kl} dV = - \int_Y u_{i,j}^* C_{ijkl} dV, \quad (21)$$

$$\int_Y u_{i,j}^* C_{ijpq} \varphi_{p,q} dV = \int_Y u_{i,j}^* C_{ijkl} \beta_{kl} dV, \quad (22)$$

$$\int_Y u_{i,j}^* C_{ijpq} \psi_{p,q} dV = \int_Y u_{i,j}^* \frac{\dot{D}}{1-D} \sigma_{ij} dV. \quad (23)$$

By substituting Eqs. (13) and (20) into Eq. (4), the following microscopic and macroscopic constitutive equation are derived;

$$\dot{\sigma}_{ij} = C_{ijpq} (\delta_{pk} \delta_{ql} + \chi_{p,q}^{kl}) \dot{\varepsilon}_{kl}^H - C_{ijkl} (\beta_{kl} - \varphi_{k,l}) - \left(\frac{\dot{D}}{1-D} \sigma_{ij} - C_{ijkl} \psi_{k,l} \right), \quad (24)$$

$$\dot{\sigma}_{ij}^H = \langle C_{ijpq} (\delta_{pk} \delta_{ql} + \chi_{p,q}^{kl}) \rangle \dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^H - \langle C_{ijkl} (\beta_{kl} - \varphi_{k,l}) \rangle - \left\langle \left(\frac{\dot{D}}{1-D} \sigma_{ij} - C_{ijkl} \psi_{k,l} \right) \right\rangle, \quad (25)$$

where δ_{ij} is Kronecker's delta, and $\langle \bullet \rangle$ represents the volume average in Y defined as $\langle \bullet \rangle = (\int_Y \bullet dV) / (\int_Y dV)$.

It is noted that the macroscopic stress and strain rates are defined as $\dot{\sigma}_{ij}^H = \langle \dot{\sigma}_{ij} \rangle$ and $\dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^H = \langle \dot{\varepsilon}_{ij} \rangle$.

3 IDENTIFICATION OF MATERIAL PARAMETERS OF EPOXY RESIN

3.1 Test Specimen and Method

The uniaxial loading-unloading tests are conducted to obtain the elasto-viscoplastic and damage properties of the epoxy resin. The scalar damage variable D is evaluated by decrement of the Young's modulus as shown in Eq. (8). Unloading phase starts when the displacement reaches a certain value, and reloading phase starts when the load reaches zero. The test specimen is made of epoxy resin (main agent: T-769/R-3233, curing agent: T-769/H-3231, Nagase ChemteX Corp.), and the dimension of the specimen is defined based on JIS-K7113 (Figure 2). The tests were performed with three constant strain rates (5.0×10^{-3} /s, 5.0×10^{-4} /s, 5.0×10^{-5} /s).

3.2 Identification of Elasto-Viscoplastic Damage Property

The representative stress-strain curve of the middle strain rate (5.0×10^{-4} /s) is shown in Figure 3. The unloading-reloading phases are conducted four times. In this study, the reduced Young's modulus is calculated by the slope of the line between two points, the stress at start of the unloading phases and the plastic strain at the zero stress points, as shown by the red lines in Figure 3. As deformation progresses, the nonlinearity can be found, and the plastic strain at the zero stress points increases. The stress-strain curves with three strain rates are shown in Figure 4. In this figure, for the understandability, the unloading-reloading phases are omitted. As a result of the tests, the epoxy resin shows viscoplastic behavior. In this study, it is assumed the scalar damage variable D increases accompanying with the plastic strain p . The relation between D and p obtained by the experiments and the approximating curve based on Eq. (7) are shown in Figure 5. Moreover, the viscoplastic parameters are identified by numerical analyses of the uniaxial tensile tests including the elasto-viscoplastic constitutive equation considering damage development. The material parameters obtained by the experiments and simulations are shown in Table 2, and the approximating curves are also shown in Figure 4.

Figure 2: Epoxy specimen for loading-unloading test, JIS-K7113.

Figure 3: Stress-strain curve of loading-unloading test (middle strain rate: 5.0×10^{-4} /s).

In general, a damage variable has critical damage variable D_{cr} which is less than 1, and it needs to be determined for each material. Then, D_{cr} is decided as 0.469 by the weibull plot shown in Figure 6. Here, F is the probability of failure.

Figure 4: Stress-strain curve of epoxy resin (experimental and simulated).

Figure 5: Relation between scalar damage variable and plastic strain.

Table 2: Material parameters of epoxy resin.

Elastic parameter	E	2.86 GPa
	ν	0.36
	ε_c	1.0
Viscoplastic parameter	$\dot{\varepsilon}_c$	$5.0 \times 10^{-5} /s$
	σ_c	648 MPa
	m	0.0393
	n	0.372
	C	10.0 MPa
	Damage parameter	d_1
d_2		1.795×10^{-2}
d_3		8.130×10^{-4}

Figure 6: Weibull plot for critical damage variable.

4 NUMERICAL DEMONSTRATION

4.1 Domain of Analysis

In this study, damage propagation of the woven CFRP laminates is analyzed numerically regarding a unit cell which consists of the fiber bundles and the epoxy matrix. The laminates are assumed to be stacked with an out-of-phase laminate configuration, which has the phase shift π in each plain fabric, to consider the laminate misalignment. A unit cell Y is defined as the domain shown by the black lines in Figure 7. Now, taking the point-symmetry with respect to the open circles shown in this figure into consideration, a reduced domain of analysis can be defined as the area indicated by the red lines in Figure 7 [11], which is called a basic cell \tilde{Y} hereafter. Additionally, the boundary value problem (18) can be rewritten by employing the point-symmetric distribution of the perturbed displacement rate $\dot{u}_i^\#$ as a boundary condition [12];

$$\int_{\tilde{Y}} u_{i,j}^* \dot{\sigma}_{ij} dV = 0. \quad (26)$$

The basic cell is divided into eight-node isoparametric elements. Here, the numbers of the nodes and elements are 4011 and 3360. Volume fraction of the fiber bundles in the laminate is defined as 61.7%, and volume fraction of the fibers in the fiber bundles is defined as 71.6% based on cross-sectional observation of the laminate. The fiber bundles in the y_1 - and y_2 -directions are called warp and weft to distinguish the fiber bundles in each direction.

4.2 Analysis Conditions

In this section, a numerical demonstration of damage propagation for the woven laminates is conducted under an uniaxial constant macroscopic tensile strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}_{11}^H = 5.0 \times 10^{-4}$ /s in the y_1 -direction.

The material parameters of the epoxy resin shown in Table 2 were used. The elastic moduli and the uniaxial strengths of the carbon fiber bundles were calculated from standard test results of the unidirectional CFRP laminates. Here, the elastic moduli were corrected inverse analytically based on the homogenization theory since the volume fraction of the fiber in the fiber bundle is different from that in the unidirectional CFRP laminates [13]. The material parameters of the fiber bundles are listed in Table 3.

(a) Isometric view.

(b) Sectional view.

Figure 7: Unit cell Y and basic cell \tilde{Y} of out-of-phase plain-woven laminates.

Table 3: Material parameters of carbon fiber bundle.

Young's modulus	E_L	168 GPa
	E_T	10.9 GPa
Shear modulus	G_{LT}	6.30 GPa
Poisson's ratio	ν_{LT}	0.279
	ν_{TT}	0.545
Tensile strength	F_L^t	2980 MPa
	F_T^t	40.1 MPa
Compressive strength	F_L^c	947 MPa
	F_T^c	143 MPa

4.3 Results of Analysis

Figure 8 is the macroscopic stress-strain curve of the woven CFRP laminates. In Figure 8, the relations between the macroscopic strain and the volume fractions of damaged elements are also shown. Here, mode L in the warp, mode T in the weft, and matrix damage are only shown because they are considered to be the main damage modes. They are the fractions with respect to volume of the weft, the warp and matrix, respectively. In addition, the damage distributions in the basic cell are shown in Figure 9-12.

At first, the edges of the weft is damaged in the transverse direction (mode T) at $\varepsilon_{11}^H = 0.00285$, and then the damage of mode T develops along the edges (Figure 9). However, the macroscopic rigidity in the loading direction and the macroscopic stress σ_{11}^H are little decreased because the rigidity of the warp is larger than the weft and the matrix. Subsequently, Figure 10 is the distribution of damage mode at $\varepsilon_{11}^H = 0.01168$, which is a occurring point of damage of mode L in the warp. The initial damage of mode L in the warp appears around the crossing area with the weft. Then, the stress increases gradually and reaches the maximum value $\sigma_{11}^H = 648$ MPa at $\varepsilon_{11}^H = 0.0155$. Figure 11 reveals that the initial damage of mode L in the warp (Figure 10) propagates in the width direction and that the damage of mode L occurs at the edge of the warp. Furthermore, matrix damage appears in the areas which are near the edge of the weft and between the weft and the warp. After that, the macroscopic stress gradually decreases as the macroscopic strain increases, and finally, the stress drops drastically at $\varepsilon_{11}^H = 0.02$. Figure 12 suggests that matrix damage develops to the upper and lower surfaces as well as around the edge of the weft. Moreover, Figure 8 confirms that the volume of warp elements damaged in mode L and damaged matrix elements sharply increase around $\varepsilon_{11}^H = 0.0155 - 0.02$. Thus, the structure is considered to result in complete fracture.

From the above numerical results, therefore, it was confirmed that damage property of the woven CFRP laminates can be evaluated correlating the microscopic damage propagation behavior with macroscopic deformation property by using the proposed method.

Figure 8: Macroscopic stress-strain curve and volume fractions of damaged elements.

Figure 9: Damage state at macroscopic strain $\varepsilon_{11}^H = 0.004$.

Figure 10: Damage state at macroscopic strain $\varepsilon_{11}^H = 0.01168$.

Figure 11: Damage state at macroscopic strain $\varepsilon_{11}^H = 0.0155$.

Figure 12: Damage state at macroscopic strain $\varepsilon_{11}^H = 0.02$.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the damage propagation behavior of the woven CFRP laminates was analyzed numerically based on the homogenization theory and the continuum damage mechanics with the viscoplasticity of the epoxy resin. First, introducing the scalar damage variable based on the continuum damage mechanics into the elasto-viscoplastic constitutive equation, the elasto-viscoplastic constitutive equation considering damage development was derived for the epoxy resin. On the other hand, the elliptic damage criterion and the second-order damage tensor were applied to carbon fiber bundles. Furthermore,

the elasto-viscoplastic constitutive equation considering damage development was introduced into the homogenization theory, and the governing equation was divided into elastic, viscoplastic and damage boundary value problems. Second, uniaxial tests including unloading and reloading phases were conducted under several strain rates to obtain the damage development equation and the viscoplastic parameters. In the numerical demonstration, assuming plain-woven laminates which has the out-of-phase laminate configuration, the unit cell and the basic cell, which is the reduced domain of analysis, are constructed. The damage propagation property of the woven CFRP laminates under uniaxial tensile loading is evaluated by the macroscopic stress-strain curve and the microscopic distribution of damage mode. The initial damage is mode T in the weft, and the damage propagation of mode L in the warp and matrix leads to degradation of the macroscopic rigidity and stress. Quantitative validation of the present analysis will be conducted experimentally in future work.

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